

Cube D series

- High Bandwidth Electrochemical Instruments

SmartNano series

- Single-Entity Analytics Software

The Cube D series is a low-noise, high-bandwidth current measurement system well suited for single-entity electrochemistry.

It consists of a pocket-size preamplifier connected by a cable to a custom data acquisition unit. The system is controlled over USB.

Specifications:

Gain: 1mV/pA, 0.5 mV/pA, 0.1 mV/pA

Bandwidth: 100 kHz

Current Measurement Rise/Fall Time < 100 μ s

RMS Noise (open input): 0.2 pArms (1 kHz), 0.5 pArms (5 kHz)

Voltage Clamp: ± 1 V (differential; not ground referenced)

Dynamic Range: ± 2 nA, ± 10 nA, ± 20 nA,

Headstage Dimensions: 12 x 7 cm

Acquisition Unit Dimensions: 13 x 13 x 4 cm

PC Interface: USB 2.0

Maximum Continuous Sample Rate: 1 MS/s

Resolution: 16-bit

The SmartNano is for single-entity electrochemical data recording based on ultra-low current recording instrument “Cube D series”. It is developed based on C#, combined with hardware driver and drawing interface component.

SmartNano contains a variety functions to satisfy the requirement of single-entity electrochemical experiments including nanopore single-molecule sensing. It allows real-time data display, data recording and bias voltage manipulation.

Specifications:

- Minimum Voltage step: 1mV;
- Current resolution: 0.625 pA ;
- Only for Windows(Win10,Win11);
- Memory usage:150 MB;

Real-time Data Display and Record

- Instrument parameter configuration
- Data record parameter configuration
- Real-time data display: Connect, Start, Record and Stop

Sampling Rate
 ▼

Low Pass Filter
 ▼

Gain
 ▼

pA

Sampling rate :1 kHz, 10 kHz, 50 kHz, 100 kHz, 250 kHz and 500 kHz optional. Low Pass Filter :5 kHz, 10 kHz and 100 kHz Optional. Gain: 1 mV/pA, 0.5 mV/pA, 0.1 mV/pA, 0.05 mV/pA and 10 mV/pA optional. This Gain should correspond to the label of the instrument headstage. The current curve error is automatically calibrated and the calibration value is displayed in the text box when the Auto button is clicked.

Record Settings

Path:

File Prefix:

Auto Recording Time: min

Set the file saving path and the prefix of the recorded data file.

The button of Connect, Start, record and Stop (from left to right)

Voltage regulation

- Constant voltage mode

^ Voltage Conf.

100 mV \updownarrow R

+10 -10

+20 -20

+50 -50

+100 -100

0 100

1000 mV \updownarrow G

mV

Auto Reset

- Automatic voltage step scan mode

IV Step Settings

low mV Hold Time s

High mV Hold Time s

Finish mV Hold Time s

Stop mV Hold Time s

Step mV Hold Time s

Save

- Pulse voltage mode

AC Settings
— □ ×

Low: mV Low Time: s

High: mV High Time: s

Real-time Data Display

- Current(blue) and Voltage(red) signal display region.

- Signal coordinate control buttons

Y Bot. pA Y Top pA ↕

Y Bot. mV Y Top mV ↕